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containing different semisolid media—N6(a), N6(b), Heh5, MSN1, and SK1—to determine which was the best for culturing hybrid rice. All the calli were transferred to plant regeneration medium SK11 (MS base + 1 mg NAA + 1 mg BAP + 0.5 mg kinetin + 30 g sucrose/liter).

The regenerated plants were transferred to half strength MS medium without hormones and left for about 3 wk to allow plantlets to harden and to ensure good root growth. Seedlings were then transferred to liquid medium (Yoshida's solution) for 1 wk before being planted in pots.

In general, a negative relationship between frequency of callus induction and regeneration was recorded (see table). For example, N6(b) had the highest callus induction (8.1%), but the frequency of regenerated plants from the calli was the lowest among the media. On the other

Response of F₁ hybrid IR58025 A/IRBB7 anthers to different media.^a

Medium	Anthers plated (no.)	Calli obtained (no.)	Calli subcultured (no.)	Calli regenerated into green plants (no.)	Green plants obtained/1,000 anthers plated (no.)
N6 (a) (2 mg 2,4-D/liter)	1320	76 (5.8)	65	7 (10.8)	6.2
N6 (b) (1 mg 2,4-D + 2 mg NAA/liter)	800	65 (8.1)	60	3 (5.0)	4.1
Heh5	500	12 (2.4)	12	4 (33.3)	8.0
MSN1	400	28 (7.0)	25	3 (12)	8.4
SK1	1500	59 (3.9)	52	14 (26.9)	10.5

^aFigures in parentheses indicate percentage of success.

hand, Heh5 induced the lowest percentage of calli (2.4%), but had the highest regeneration rate.

A more important index of success is the percentage of green seedlings ultimately recovered. Using this index, SK1

produced 10.5 green seedlings per 1,000 anthers plated, SMN1 produced 8.4, and Heh5 produced 8.0. Thus, to obtain a minimum of 150 seedlings, at least 15,000 anthers must be inoculated in best medium SK1. ■

Yield potential

Effect of seed size on grain yield of rice

S. K. Varshney, S. K. Sinha, and B. N. Jha, Seed Technology Department, Tirhut College of Agriculture (TCA), Dholi 843121, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India

Grading is an integral step in seed processing for obtaining quality seeds. We investigated the effect of seed size on rice yield.

Ungraded, graded, and undersized seeds of two popular rice varieties were procured from the seed processing plant at TCA and characterized (Table 1).

Table 1. Characteristics of different grades of seeds used initially in the study. TCA, Bihar, India.

Treatment	1,000-grain wt (g)	Germination (%)	Seedling length (cm)
<i>Mahsuri</i>			
Graded	15.7	81	20.8
Ungraded	15.0	72	18.8
Undersized	10.0	50	16.9
<i>Sujata</i>			
Graded	22.5	76	22.7
Ungraded	22.0	76	22.7
Undersized	16.5	52	20.0
SE ±	1.8	5	0.9

Table 2. Effect of seed size on grain yield and quality of seed produced from different rice grades. TCA, Bihar, India. 1991 and 1992 wet seasons.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		1,000-grain wt (g)	Germination ^a (%)	Seedling length (cm)
	1991	1992			
<i>Size</i>					
Graded	3.4	4.6	22.1	83.8	21.4
Ungraded	2.9	3.4	21.1	82.8	21.5
Undersized	2.5	3.1	19.7	81.5	22.1
<i>Variety</i>					
Mahsuri	2.5	2.8	20.5	82.8	21.8
Sujata	3.4	4.3	21.5	82.5	21.5
CD (5%) (Size)	0.5	0.6	ns ^b	ns	ns
CD (5%) (Variety)	0.4	0.5	ns	ns	ns
CV (%)	14.6	17.3	11.6	1.5	11.1

^aAnalysis based on angular transformed values. ^bns = not significant.

Seeds that passed through a screen with 1.85-mm oblong slits were categorized as undersized and those that did not were categorized as graded.

Seedlings were raised following standard practices. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications and 5 × 2 m² plot size. Two seedlings per hill were transplanted at a spacing of 20 cm between rows and 15 cm within rows for each of the six treatments in 1991 and 1992 kharif (wet) seasons. Recommended practices were followed to raise the crop.

Seed yield was recorded for each treatment and the data were analyzed statistically. We also recorded the 1,000-grain weight, germination percentage for 400 seeds (100 seeds from each replication), and seedling length from the seeds produced with different grades.

The graded seed of Mahsuri was superior to the others for germination percentage and seedling length (Table 2). However, for Sujata, graded and ungraded seeds were similar for all characters. Undersized seeds were poor for these attributes in both varieties.

Seed size affected significantly seed yields for different grades in both varieties (Table 2). The graded seeds gave significantly higher yields than did the other seed grades. Ungraded and undersized seeds did not differ statistically in grain yield. Sujata, however, was significantly superior to Mahsuri for seed yield. The interaction between seed size and variety was not significant, which emphasizes the importance of grading for obtaining quality rice seed and for realizing a variety's yield potential. Using ungraded or undersized seed to produce a crop may adversely affect yield potential and should be discouraged.

No marked difference existed in the seed quality obtained from different grades of seeds. The main effect of seed size is on the production potential or grain yield and not on the quality of the seeds produced from them. ■

Competitive ability of medium-duration rices for grain yield

N. Kulkarni, Agricultural Research Institute (ARI), Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

Varietal mixtures differ in their efficiency in capturing resources to produce higher yields compared with when varieties are grown in pure stands. We studied the competitive ability of all possible mixtures of five varieties in 1992 and six varieties in 1993. These varieties had long, slender grains and medium duration (130-150 d). Two varieties were mixed in equal proportions, using all possible combinations.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design repeated three times during 1992 and 1993 wet seasons. Each entry was planted in a six-row plot, 5.4 m in length, and spaced at 15 cm between and within rows. One-month-old seedlings of the mixtures and of the pure varieties were planted in 1992 and 45-d-old seedlings in 1993.

Grain yield data and percent increase over best pure varieties and check Surekha were recorded (Table 1). In 1992, two varietal mixtures—RDR536 + Surekha and RDR536 + Saleem—yielded

Table 1. Grain yield of varietal mixtures and pure varieties.

Varietal mixture/ pure variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	% increase over	
		Best pure variety	Check variety
1992			
RDR536 + Raja Vadlu	8.2	0.0	21.1
RDR536 + Divya	8.0	-2.4	18.2
RDR536 + Surekha	9.4	14.6	39.9
RDR536 + Saleem	9.2	12.2	36.2
Raja Vadlu + Divya	6.8	-9.3	0.3
Raja Vadlu + Surekha	8.0	6.6	19.0
Raja Vadlu + Saleem	7.7	2.7	14.6
Divya + Surekha	7.6	11.7	12.0
Divya + Saleem	7.3	19.3	9.2
Surekha + Saleem	7.2	5.9	5.9
RDR536	8.2		
Raja Vadlu	7.5		
Divya	5.9		
Surekha	6.8		
Saleem	6.1		
CD	0.8		
CV (%)	5.6		
1993			
RDR536 + Raja Vadlu	5.8	9.3	12.6
RDR536 + Surekha	5.9	9.3	14.1
RDR536 + Saleem	4.9	-9.2	-4.9
RDR536 + RNR 32341	5.7	7.4	11.2
RDR536 + CSR13	6.0	11.1	12.7
Raja Vadlu + Surekha	5.9	15.7	14.1
Raja Vadlu + Saleem	4.8	0.0	1.9
Raja Vadlu + RNR32341	5.6	3.7	7.8
Raja Vadlu + CSR13	5.5	1.9	7.0
Surekha + Saleem	4.8	-5.9	-7.8
Surekha + RNR32341	5.4	0.0	5.6
Surekha + CSR13	5.2	-3.7	1.4
Saleem + RNR32341	5.4	0.0	5.6
Saleem + CSR13	4.5	-1.8	-11.9
RNR32341 + CSR13	5.3	-1.8	2.1
RDR536	5.4		
Raja Vadlu	4.8		
Surekha	5.1		
Saleem	4.6		
RNR32341	5.4		
CSR13	5.4		
CD	0.5		
CV (%)	4.8		

Table 2. General combining ability effects.^a

	1992	1993
RDR536	0.280**	0.153**
Raja Vadlu	0.004	-0.006
Divya	-0.191**	-
Surekha	-0.001	0.013
Saleem	-0.093*	-0.274**
CSR13	-	0.031
RNR32341	-	0.081
SE (g/ii)	0.038	0.04

*, ** = significant at 5 and 1% level, respectively.

12% more grain than when planted individually and 36% more grain than Surekha. Other varietal mixtures also outyielded the check.

In 1993, Raja Vadlu + Surekha yielded 15.7% more than the best yields

of the sole varieties; RDR536 + Raja Vadlu, 9.3%; RDR536 + CSR13, 11.1%; and collectively, about 13% more than the check. These combinations were phenotypically uniform, which is desirable. The general combining ability effects are estimated in Table 2, treating the experiment as mechanical diallel. RDR536 in the various mixtures produced more grain and possessed significantly positive general combining ability effects in both years.

This study revealed superior performance of varietal mixtures compared with that of pure varieties. Therefore, it is worthwhile to test more varietal mixtures to exploit their competitive ability. ■

Pest resistance— insects

Resistance of medium-duration rice cultivars to caseworm and leaffolder

H. P. Patnaik, K. M. Samal, and S. Mohapatra, Regional Research Station, Keonjhar 758002, Orissa, India

Caseworm (CW) *Nymphula depunctalis* (Guenée) and leaffolder (LF) *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* (Guenée) incidences have been high in recent years in the rice-growing area of the north central plateau of Orissa State, India. We evaluated 12 promising medium-duration (120-135 d) rice cultivars for resistance to these pests during 1992 and 1993 wet seasons (WS).

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Each cultivar was transplanted in 4 × 2-m plots. The percentage of leaves damaged by CW was recorded at 30 d after transplanting (DT) and that by LF at 50 DT. For each plot, we randomly selected 20 hills and examined five leaves per hill. Low precipitation (996 mm) in 1992 WS favored LF incidence while high precipitation (1200 mm) in 1993 WS favored CW incidence.

Cultivar RP2327-318 had high insect damage and low yields in both 1992 and 1993. In contrast, cultivar P622-629